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D.1.4

Exploitation Handbook

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
DoA	Description of Action
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSC	Logistics Service Client
LSP	Logistics Service Provider
3PL	Third-Party Logistics
IT	Information Technology
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NPV	Net Present Value
IRR	Internal Return Rate

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Executive Summary

According to the Description of Action the task 5.1 leading to this deliverable is a “guidelines document and set of templates for product idea definition, innovation management including market and competition analysis, business planning including financial indicators and business cases adoption and extension”.

This Exploitation Handbook provides an approach to develop plans for new businesses based on CLUSTERS 2.0 results based on three phases:

Ideation, where potential business ideas are identified and convincingly formulated, looking at CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions from the point of view of user needs from the market. The proposed methodology is based on the “job to be done” concept, that describes a new product idea in terms of customer, need and circumstance. By looking at certain “jobs” that are not satisfactorily addressed for a customer in certain circumstances, opportunities for new products and services are found. Also important is to identify the features the customer looks for when looking for a solution to that particular problem, and at the barriers that customers face in trying to solve the problem with existing products.

Strategy, where a product or service idea is translated into an innovative proposition which is appealing to the customer, clearly differentiates from competition and addresses the right market segments. This is done by identifying competing products, i.e., the set of common solutions currently used to get the job done, and positioning our solution against competition. For this we propose to use the approach and tools defined in the Blue Ocean Strategy, a well-known theory and methodological framework for innovation management. At this point a detailed business model is developed, including decisions on customer relationships, sales channels, revenue flows, value chain configuration and partnerships, key activities and resources, and finally on the foreseen cost structure.

Implementation, where concrete plans and detailed estimations are prepared to support the transition from idea and value proposition to business implementation. This phase includes planning in detail the next development stages to bring the product on the market, and the investments required. Marketing activities have also to be planned, and sales volumes estimated according to a set strategy for expansion on the market. The cost structure has to be quantified based on assumptions about the needed resources and organization, the investments required and the expected market growth. In this way a forecast financial plan is prepared that covers industrialisation of the business idea, launch on the market and business operation, over a 5 years period. This allows to assess the financial performance of the new business over a sufficiently long time-horizon. To this purpose, financial indicators are calculated that allow company managers, partners and investors to evaluate the business idea potential and risks. Two main indicators are proposed, well known to the business community: the Net Present Value (NPV), an estimation of an investment worth based on actualized cash-flow estimations, and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR), a measure of an investment’s profitability to be used for comparison with other forms of investment.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of Document

The objective of this document is to provide a handbook and guideline to support the CLUSTERS 2.0 partners in preparing, discussing and presenting plans for the exploitation of the Project's solutions and results.

This handbook will provide:

1. a recommended approach and methodology to be applied for the exploitation planning process into three main phases, respectively aimed at:
 - i) identification of the CLUSTERS 2.0 business solutions that will be exploited by different partners in the consortium;
 - ii) positioning of the partners in the CLUSTERS 2.0 business ecosystem for each identified solution;
 - iii) preparation of the business and investment plans for each partner to bring the solution on the market.
2. for each phase, a set of guidelines, instruments and examples that should be applied by the partners to address the main questions arising in the subsequent methodological steps.
3. detailed guidelines on the recommended state-of-the-art approaches, business planning and business modelling tools, which are further documented in the Annexes and References Sections.

In the second part of the project, this methodology and guidelines will be used by the partners to develop the draft and final exploitation plans, to be further discussed in the Exploitation Workshops and documented in Deliverable D1.5.

1.2 Intended audience

The main audience that should be interested in this deliverable are all CLUSTERS 2.0 partners interested in industrial and commercial exploitation of the project results. This includes mainly the industrial partners but also research organisations intending to exploit the knowledge developed in the project in market-oriented activities (e.g., university spin-offs launched to exploit research results).

1.3 Deliverable objectives

This deliverable is the first output of task T1.4 “Commercial Exploitation” and provides the overall methodology to be implemented by the CLUSTERS 2.0 throughout this Task until the end of the project. The approach here described will be explained and applied during the exploitation workshops foreseen at months 15, 24 and 30, and it will result in the preparation of draft and final Exploitation Plans for the involved project partners.

The document contents are as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the overall approach and timing for the exploitation process.
- Section 3 provides guidelines for business idea definition and identification of target market and customers.
- Section 4 introduces the main aspects related to business strategy definition, including features and barriers identification, competition analysis and positioning on the market. It also provides guidelines for the definition and selection of the individual stakeholders

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business models.

- Section 5 provides guidelines to create a convincing plan to successfully bring the business idea on the market, planning the required product development, marketing and delivery activities and demonstrating the financial as well as technical feasibility of the project to the company management, partners and potential investors.
- The Annexes Section contains templates and tools that can be used by the project partners in their exploitation planning.

2. Exploitation approach

2.1 Definitions

Table 1 – CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation definitions

CLUSTERS 2.0 Solutions	One of the three main solutions that are being developed in CLUSTERS and will be piloted in the Living Labs. These solutions are studied and validated from the business point of view in Tasks T1.1, T1.2 and T1.3.
Reference Business Ecosystem	The different types of stakeholders who interact to implement, deliver and make use of the solution on the market. The CLUSTERS 2.0 ecosystem is studied in Task 1.1 and documented in Deliverable D1.1.
Reference Business Models	The business models of the different types of stakeholders in the ecosystem, as they are now and as they should evolve due to implementation of the CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions. The current business models are analysed in Deliverable D1.1 and the potential business models evolutions are discussed in Deliverable D1.2
Business Idea	The business idea is a potential new business, based on CLUSTERS solutions, that the partners intend to explore for potential exploitation on the market. The business idea can be explored by a single partner or jointly by a group of CLUSTERS partners who would like to exploit it together.
Exploitation Plan	The exploitation plan describes the strategy, goals, commercial plan and financials for the exploitation of a Business Idea. The exploitation plan is a concrete implementation plan of the Business Idea. It includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - detailed estimations of the planned investments to industrialise the product; - detailed plans and targets for marketing and sales activities; - price and sales performances assumptions; - detailed cost estimations; - estimation of funding requirements; - financial performances indicators.

2.2 Exploitation approach overview

The approach proposed in the present document takes a different perspective on exploitation planning, compared to the methods commonly applied in other EU projects. Typically, exploitation tends to focus mostly on preparing business plans, as traditionally made of sales forecasts and marketing plans and financial simulations. Innovation is seen mostly from a company's internal perspective, following approaches such as Porter's Value Chain, Balanced Scorecard and Boston Group Matrix.

Although we recognize the importance of the above aspects, we are convinced that innovations as envisioned in the CLUSTERS 2.0 project require a collaborative approach in all stages, from formulation to implementation of the business idea. In our project, innovation

is not an individual company exercise, but must be undertaken with the involvement of all the relevant actors participating in designing and implementing CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions. Therefore our approach foresees a close interaction with solutions design in Workpackages WP2, WP3 and WP4, and with solutions experimentation in the Living Labs.

The CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation approach includes three main phases:

1. **Ideation.** In this phase potential ideas of products and services are identified, based on CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions and starting from user needs from the market. Here the goal is to identify, prioritize and formulate promising ideas for successful exploitation on the market. This phase is carried out in close interaction with WP2, WP3 and WP4, where solutions are designed and developed, and with the industrial partners involved in the Living Lab.
2. **Strategy.** In this phase the most promising business ideas are selected and refined through performance attributes analysis and utility testing. Here the focus is on translating the original idea into an innovative proposition which is appealing to the customer, clearly differentiates from competition and addresses the right market segments with the right price. This phase is carried out collaboratively by group of partners who are all involved, with different roles, in the commercial exploitation of a certain business idea.
3. **Implementation.** In this phase the right implementation model and plan are defined for each of the selected business ideas, through the steps of business model formulation, business planning and evaluation of alternative plans. This phase is carried out individually by each partner according to its intended role in the exploitation of the business idea, according to the partner's own target market, its assets (including intellectual property) and planned investments.

The following Table 2 lists the main questions to be addressed by the involved stakeholders in each phase, and the corresponding content to be produced in the Exploitation Plan in reply to those questions.

Table 2 – Phases in CLUSTERS 2.0 Exploitation Approach

Phase	Questions to be answered	Content to be produced
1. Ideation	Who are your target customers? What products and services are you offering? Why are these products and services relevant to customers?	- Target customers and needs identification - Value proposition formulation - Features and Barriers identification
2. Strategy	How do you intend to position your product on the market? How do you differentiate from competitors? What is your intended business model? What role do you intend to play in the CLUSTERS 2.0 ecosystem?	- Competitors identification - Competitive positioning - Business Model description
3. Implementation	What is needed to make the product market-ready?	- Technical development plan

	<p>How will you promote and sell the product? When will you start and how much do you intend to sell?</p> <p>How will you protect your IPRs? How will you manage joint IPRs with your business partners?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercialization plan - Financial plan and indicators (return on investment, profitability, ...) - IPR strategy
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The following Sections 3, 4 and 5 address sequentially the three above phases, proposing templates as well as selected tools and methodologies to be applied in each phase.

2.3 Exploitation timing

The three phases in CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation planning process will be carried out in sequence, throughout the duration of the project as shown in Figure 1.

The exploitation activities will proceed in parallel with the research and innovation tasks in WP2, WP3 and WP4 and Living Labs, following the project's iterative approach. Each iteration will provide new input to exploitation planning, in the form of solution ideas and living lab scoping (Iteration 1), initial assessment of the solution and feedback from users (Iteration 2) and quantitative indications on the solutions' benefits and costs (Iteration 3).

Three exploitation workshops are planned:

- Month 15: to present the initial solutions, ecosystem analysis, current business models and the exploitation methodology. This workshop will prepare finalisation of phase 1, Ideation, leading to identification and description of CLUSTERS 2.0 business ideas.
- Month 24: to collaborative build the strategy and business model for each of the identified solutions, through the participation of the involved partners and stakeholders. This workshop will prepare finalisation of phase 2, Strategy, leading to identification of the involved partners' business models.
- Month 30: to start the planning and financial feasibility analysis of the target business ideas, based on each partner's market estimations, goals and investments. This workshop will prepare finalisation of phase 3, Implementation, leading to definition of exploitation plans including quantified targets, milestones and financials.

The three phases utilize the reference knowledge produced by other WP1 Tasks and documented in the following Deliverables:

- D1.1 "Market & Business Ecosystem analysis" supports Ideation, by scoping of CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions from a business perspective, analysing the ecosystem structure, the stakeholders current business models and the current and foreseen market scenario.
- D1.2 "Business Models Innovation" supports Strategy, by identifying the business models changes, or entire new business models, that the partners can refer to when defining their own business model.
- D1.3 "Business Models Validation", although being prepared in parallel to the final Implementation phase, can provide quantitative information on the business models technical and financial viability (e.g., costs) to help preparation of the final exploitation plans.

Figure 1 Timeline of CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation activities

3. Ideation

3.1 Purpose

The ideation Phase starts from the CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions, as they result from the project's Research and Innovation activities, and it has the purpose of identifying and defining relevant business ideas exploiting the solutions on the market

To identify a new business idea means being able to answer the following questions:

- Which customers are targeted by your solution?
- Why is this target market particularly interesting for your company?
- What customer problem does the idea solve? What customer need does it meet?
- What solution are you offering to address the need?
- What kind of products or services are included in the solution? What do you intend to sell?

3.2 Ideation template

Table 3 Ideation phase template

Target Market Sector and Client profile
<p><u>Market sector:</u> Indicate the target market of your solution, i.e., the community of customers that are experiencing the problem you are trying to solve with your solution. Is it a niche or high volume market? Is it a mature or growing market? Are you already present on the market or is it a new one for you?</p> <p><u>Customer profile:</u> Identify who will use the product / service (user) and who will pay for the product / service (customer). Often user and customer coincide, but in some cases they may not. Describe the key characteristics of the customer that make him/she the ideal target for the solution you are proposing.</p>
Problem to solve and business opportunity
<p><u>Problem to solve:</u> Describe the problem that exists in the target sector, that your solution intends to solve, e.g., a social, economic, environmental or safety problem. Be careful to look at the problem not from your viewpoint as the solution provider but from the customer viewpoint: this is his/her problem you are trying to solve.</p> <p><u>Business opportunity:</u> Describe the business opportunity that is there on the market for your solution: is there a gap in the market that nobody has filled before? Are there market opportunities not yet exploited? Are there favourable conditions to approach the market? Try to demonstrate why is it worth investing in the solution and why now.</p>

Value Proposition and Solution	
<p><u>Value Proposition:</u> The core value delivered by your solution, to be communicated to and acknowledged by the market. A value proposition is a statement which identifies clear, measurable and demonstrable benefits customers get when buying a particular service or product.</p> <p><u>Solution:</u> Describe the product / service which constitutes your solution to the customer's problem. Describe it accurately in its main parts (components, services,..) and its key features. The solution's features should directly refer to the problem to be solved and the business opportunity.</p>	
User Needs vs. Solution	
Target User needs	Solution's benefits
Specify the needs of target users. These are specific problems (or "pains") the customers feel and have willingness to pay to see them solved.	Specify how your solution meets the specific customer need, motivating the customer to buy your product / service.
User Need 1	...
...	...
User Need n	...

3.3 Ideation methods and tools

Identifying target customers

As a first step, the target customers have to be identified in a specific way. For innovative solutions, as developed in CLUSTERS 2.0 customers have to be sought outside of the company's current target or captive clients. It is likely that the customers are to be found among the "nonconsumers", i.e., those who are not currently served by your business, or among those who are showing signs of tiredness and disaffection for your current offering.

Therefore, instead of trying to understand the market by interviewing your current users or your most affectionate customer, the attention should be focused on those who *do not* buy in the current solutions, or are dissatisfied about the product and service they receive.

The target customers are to be sought for in two main categories:

- **Non-consumers.** These are the ones who are not currently using any solution for the

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problem you are trying to solve. They do so because of **barriers**, i.e., constraints that make current solutions inadequate for a certain category of users, usually determine non-consumption. These barriers have been classified in [2] in four main types:

- **Skill** barriers. User lacks prerequisite skills.
 - **Cost** barriers. Available solutions have prohibitive costs for the user.
 - **Access** barriers. User does not buy because current solutions are unavailable in certain locations or contexts.
 - **Time** barriers. The solution is too cumbersome or time consuming.
- **Overshot customers.** Overshooting means that users are unwilling to buy in improved products or new versions of a product. The customers need a solution but they do not want to pay the extra costs for improvements on that solution. Overshot customers are typical target of “disruption”. Indeed we offer opportunities for disruptive innovation strategies: Whenever overshot customers appear, there is a chance to offer them “good enough” performance at lower cost and/or greater convenience. In this case innovation mostly concerns the business model: technology advances, process and value chain improvements allow to provide the same product or service for less.

Example

A provider of a logistic services online booking platform might define its target as the following:

- *Customer:* logistic services provider running a own fleet of trucks and trailers for deliveries to shops in urban areas.

As there is a very limited participation of these kind of carrier services providers to the booking platform, this may be a case of non-consumption. Therefore it makes sense to investigate the exiting barriers.

- Skill barriers: trucking companies personnel is mostly engage in operations, with limited time to sit in front of a computer and familiarize with a marketplace platform.
- Cost barriers: independent urban deliveries companies have very low margins and may have no interest for uncertain-return investments, no matter the low cost.
- Access barriers: potential customers doubt that they will find their all of their business partners in the platform already, limiting their willingness to join: a typical “chicken and egg” problem.

Finding user needs

The next step is to find opportunities for your solution to address specific user needs. According to the “job to be done” concept from Christensen [1], a well known method in innovation management, the task here is finding *a useful job that is not satisfactorily performed for a certain customer in clearly defined circumstances.*

According to Christensen’s method, a job statement takes the form:

[Customer] wants to solve a [problem] in this [circumstance]

A job definition includes three main elements:

- The **customer** identified in precise terms as somebody who is trying to solve an important problem to solve, linked to his/her own goals and motivations.
- The **problem** itself, currently or not satisfactorily addressed by existing solutions accessible to the customer.

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- The **circumstance**, i.e., the specific conditions under which the problem is experienced by the customer, that are relevant to the solution.

The “job to be done” method can help you to state in unambiguous terms what problem the customer wants to solve.

The job to be done statement must be specific about the customer need, but also about the circumstance where this need manifest itself.

Also, it is important to reach a level of detail sufficient to identify all and only those “jobs” that our solution can perform, i.e., that match our solution’s functions and features and the capabilities and resources of our business.

Creating a “job tree” can help to this purpose. The tree has at its root some fundamental but general need of the customer, that is then progressively detailed into more precise needs and circumstances. The job tree leafs represent jobs defined with sufficient precision to be the start of our business ideas. See in Annex 1.A.1 the “job tree” template and description.

Looking at customer objectives

A job is the definition of a problem the customer wants solved, but by itself does not complete the analysis of users needs. When looking to solutions for their problem, customers have “objectives” on “how” the problem should be solved. They use these objectives as criteria to evaluate the available solutions to their problem.

Looking at the customer objectives helps to identify the functional and non-functional features our solution should have, on which basis it will be compared to competition.

Example

Job to be done
Urban delivery service wants to have visibility on cargo bundling opportunities
Customer objectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time visibility of delivery requests. - Possibility to bundle cargo from different shippers. - Easy access and presentation of data for the internal users customer. - Easy integration of monitoring data with clients systems. - ...

Looking at adoption barriers

The term “adoption barriers” is used to indicate constraints of any type preventing the customer to adopt a certain solution. As explained above, adoption barriers are usually referring to skill, cost, access and time constrains.

Looking at the customer adoption barriers allows to identify further product features that the product should have to favour adoption. If the product and business model are conceived to lower these barriers, customers will feel more comfortable in adopting the solution.

Example

Job to be done
Urban delivery service wants to have visibility on cargo bundling opportunities

Adoption barriers

- Sharing real time data across systems difficult and expensive.
- Sales and planning personnel need training on the new system.
- Most clients will continue to be managed through the traditional system.
- ...

Setting priorities

The analysis of customer needs using the job-to-be-done concept is a comprehensive exercise where many “jobs” can be identified, all potentially addressed by the solution. However in most cases it is better to focus first on the most important jobs, those representing the most important problems for the customer.

To this purpose, problems can be prioritized based on the following criteria:

- **Relevance.** How relevant is for the customer to solve the problem?
- **Frequency.** How common is the problem among the customers population? Is it rare or commonplace?
- **Frustration.** How much pain does the problem cause to the customer?

4. Strategy

4.1 Purpose

The Strategy Phase starts from the potential business ideas based on CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions, as they result from Ideation phase, and it has the purpose of defining how the product will look and will be positioned on the market, and what kind of business model is needed to do that.

To correctly define the strategy for a new business idea the following questions have to be answered:

- What is innovative about your product or service?
- How can you differentiate yourself from competition?
- Who are your competitors? What substitutes are there for your product?
- Is the Unique Selling Proposition formulated precisely and from the customer's perspective?
- How large is the whole market? How large is the market you are interested in? How will it develop?
- What does your company's business model look like?
- What key activities and resources within the business model will the company perform?

4.2 Strategy template

Table 4 Strategy phase template

Competitors analysis
<p><u>Competitors analysis:</u> Describe whether the product / service has direct or indirect competitors on the European and global market. If so, specify how big they are, their market share and how much they can hinder the entry of your new product / service.</p> <p><u>Competitor 1:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main characteristics of competitor 1 - <p><u>Competitor N:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main characteristics of competitor N - ... <p><u>Competitive positioning:</u> Indicate how the product differs from the competition in terms of key performance attributes (e.g.: costs, ease-of use, functionality, benefits for the users and the society, ..). Use the table below with the names of alternative products and compare them with the new product according to the selected features.</p>

Competitive positioning				
Relevant features	Solution 1	...	Solution M	<u>Our Solution</u>
Feature 1	Assign a relative score to the solution on this feature (e.g., low/average/high compared to the other solutions). Motivate the score.	...	Assign a relative score to the solution on this feature (e.g., low/average/high compared to the other solutions). Motivate the score.	Assign a relative score to the solution on this feature (e.g., low/average/high compared to the other solutions). Motivate the score.
...
Feature N
Business Model				
<p><u>Business and Revenue Model:</u> Indicate what the company sells (standard product and add on, software licenses...) and the revenue streams, indicate the value proposition, motivate price positioning, indicate key activities (R&D, tests, certifications, production, marketing/dissemination, post-sales assistance...), indicate sales channels (direct sale via ecommerce, sale through agents...), indicate the expected time-to-market and distribution, indicate cost structure.</p> <p><u>Key Stakeholders</u> Describe project stakeholders, which may be: users or customers of the product / service, financier, key sub-suppliers, key external consultants, government agency officials (who must, for example, provide important authorizations for the project), representatives of local authorities (e.g. ports, municipalities), media, etc. For each of the previous stakeholder categories you should mention some names or, even better, some contacts. If these contacts do not exist, describe a plan to obtain this information.</p>				
SWOT Analysis				
<p><u>Strengths:</u> Indicate the internal strengths of the company and of the product / service (for example: X years of experience in the sector, patented product, contact with major networks in the sector).</p>		<p><u>Weaknesses:</u> Indicate the internal weaknesses of the company and of the product / service (for example: lack of financial resources, lack of staff, long time-to-market).</p>		
<p><u>Opportunities:</u> Indicate the opportunities existing outside the company and its product / service (for example: growing market, low barriers to entry, few competitors, state incentives...).</p>		<p><u>Threats:</u> Indicate risks external to the company and to the product / service (for example: change of European directives, entry of new competitors, non-perceived product / service value...).</p>		

4.3 Strategy methods and tools

Competitors analysis

To identify competitors' solutions is the first step in strategy definition for a new business. These have to be described in relation to the user needs previously identified, that our solution is planning to satisfy for the users.

The right strategy approach to launch an innovative product is to map the marketplace in terms of what is available now to solve a certain problem, focusing on the job-to-be-done rather than on the technology, size and operational performance of competitors.

In our exploitation approach, we should consider as **competitors** *any existing product/service constituting a valid alternative for the customer to solve the problem we are addressing.*

Independently of how innovative we think our idea is, it is quite unlikely that the problem we target is completely new and unsolved. Most likely, our target users have faced the problem in the past and found alternative solutions. These solutions can be completely different in terms of technology and business model, they can also be classified in different industrial sectors, some of them can be products and other services. Nevertheless, if they address the same problem we should consider them as competitors.

It may even seem that the problem we are targeting is really unaddressed, that nobody has tried to solve it before us. In such case, it is highly recommended to take a second look: there may be technically feasible solutions to the problem, but they have not reached the market because of cost, accessibility or other barriers.

Based on these considerations you should create a **list of competing solutions**, including all products and services of any type the users buy to get the job done

Example

For our city logistic services online booking platform competitors could be the following:

- Existing freight marketplace, on national, EU or global level
- Local shipping agents and forwarders.

While the first type of competitor is technically similar to our product, the second one is not. Nevertheless traditional intermediaries are commonly used by our target customers for their sales needs, and we should face them as competitors.

Competitive positioning

Competitive positioning means comparing key features of our solution with competing products, to explore alternative differentiation strategies. This can be done by identifying the key characteristics of the solution that are valuable for the user, and using these to differentiate from competition. To this purpose we can look at the list of product features and barriers identified in the Ideation phase, when we were looking at the customer's problem.

We will call these **performance attributes** and, following the Blue Ocean approach [2], we will use a simple but powerful tool to describe your strategy with reference to these attributes: the Strategy Canvas.

The Strategy Canvas is a simple two-axes diagram, where:

- The horizontal axis captures the performance attributes, i.e., the range of factors the industry competes on and invests in. You should select those factors that, according to your judgment, are the important ones to be taken into account for strategy formulation. As we will see later on, the range of attributes may change along the

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formulation process as we revise and refine our strategy.

- The vertical axis captures the user satisfaction level achieved by a solution across all these key performance attributes. A high score means that a company offers buyers more performances and hence invests more in that factor.

So the value curve, the basic component of the strategy canvas is a graphic depiction of a product's relative performance across its industry's factors of competition.

Example

The Strategy Canvas in Figure 2 shows the value curves of different solutions performing the job “provide visibility on cargo bundling opportunities” for urban delivery companies. Our solution, marked as “Our solution” (green line), corresponds to the innovative idea to build an online demand-offer matching platform to visualize and manage tracking of individual items. There are at least two alternative solutions to the one we propose:

- “Freight marketplace” (blue line): customers register on an existing freight marketplace, that matches services offer and demand on a larger scale;
- “Local forwarders” (red line): customers partner up with local intermediaries to get business, as they do in their business as usual;

Figure 2 Competitive positioning example

Blue Ocean strategy is a powerful methodology with several concepts and tools that can help in CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation. Some of them are briefly illustrated in Annex 1.A.2.

Business Model definition

After definition of the product idea and strategy in terms of target customers, needs and positioning strategy, the next step is to find the right model to implement the new business idea.

Business Modelling is a widely studied subject, and some comprehensive business modelling frameworks exist in literature. Among these, the Osterwalder framework [6] has been adopted for CLUSTERS 2.0 Business Modelling activities, that will be documented in Deliverables D1.1, for the current business models analysis, and D1.2, for the evolution of these models thanks to CLUSTERS solutions.

For exploitation planning purposes it is important to specify a detailed business model for implementing the business idea, taking into account the reference business models defined in the above Deliverables as well as the operating context of the involved project partners, in terms of organization and available resources.

With reference to the Osterwalder framework categories, the exploitation plan business model should be precisely specified in terms of:

- Value proposition is the core subject of the Ideation generation and Strategy phases (see previous sections). At this stage further details will be added to fully specify the offered products and services, including detailed product definitions and features specifications.
- Customer segments result from identification of the potential market performed in the ideation stage. Further details must be added at this point, defining the target customer segments in both qualitative and quantitative terms.
- Customer relationships have to be defined in detail, e.g., by determining whether service agreements are needed for one or more customer segments, as well as the purpose and scope of such agreements. Customer relationships are also likely to be affected by innovation strategy decisions taken in previous stages.
- Channels determine the direct or indirect ways to reach target customer segments. These are dependent on the company's market presence and established partnerships, but new channels are often needed to implement innovative business models.
- Revenue streams define how income is generated by the business, and are thus dependent on the value proposition and pricing models defined in the Ideation phase. At this stage precise indications are needed of cash generated by unit of the different products/services.
- Partner network is especially important for products, such as CLUSTERS solutions, resulting from complex value chains and relying on network externalities. The main partners required to deliver the offered product/service must be identified, both as roles in the value chain and, wherever possible, as precisely identified organizations. For each key partner, the following issues have to be addressed in detail:
 - o Products or services supplied by the partner and contributing to the overall offer of our business. Only key contributions are relevant, i.e., providing significant value to our business' customers.
 - o Long-term agreements. "Spot" relationships, built on a case-by-case basis to solve specific customer projects are not suitable for key value chain partners. These will require long-term agreements, lasting one or more years and based on common investment and revenue targets.
 - o Customer relationship. Depending on the partner product, size and organization, different kinds of customer-facing agreements have to be established. These are critical in determining our business position on the market, and hence the value of the business itself. The range of options varies from "Value Added Reselling" of branded products (we simply deliver and install some other company's solution), to embedding of third-party products into our own solution, to joint ventures where a new product is developed and branded by cooperating value-chain partners.

Clusters 2.0

- Financial agreements. Every key business relationship will entail financial obligations between the parties. These may range from ad-hoc price lists, royalties, mutual investments, up to shares owned in a joint venture newco. Regardless of their type, key partners' agreements have to be analyzed in detail in financial terms, as these have a significant impact on costs and revenue streams.

It is very important that the Business Model includes a clear specification of the partners network. Key partners should be precisely indicated. If some partner is still not known, e.g., because different options are being evaluated or agreements are still under definition, it is important that the partner role in the value chain is described, and plans are provided for the inclusion of a definite entity in that role within a proper timeframe.

- Key activities are those central to delivering value to the user and to attract customers identified in the idea definition and idea shaping stages. Key activities should be distinctive of our business, representing areas where we have to excel. Typically these activities should be carried out internally, as they mark our role in the value chain. The option to outsource some key activities should be carefully analyzed and motivated, and if really necessary it should be sustained by carefully designed partnership agreements.
- Key resources are material or immaterial assets that are essential to our business. Typically they are know-how, software products, patents, infrastructure and production facilities that are key to deliver value to our customers. As for key activities, key resources are dependent on the value proposition resulting from the idea definition and idea shaping stages.
- Cost structure includes the main costs incurred by the business to operate, falling into three main categories:
 - *Cost of goods/services sold*. These are costs that can be attributed to each unit of delivered product or service, as they are directly related to the production or delivery activities.
 - *Sales and marketing expenses*. These are the costs incurred for reaching the customer segments, including, e.g.: marketing management, advertising, customer relationships management, sales administration.
 - *General and administrative expenses*. These are all the costs not directly related to producing or selling the product/service, but necessary to sustain the business, including, e.g., general administration, personnel management, ICT, buildings, secretarial staff.

5. Implementation

5.1 Purpose

The Implementation phase starts from the business ideas, positioning strategy and business models, resulting from the previous phases, and it has the purpose of defining how the product will be brought on the market, which are the steps required and the financials aspects.

This is final step in exploitation planning and describes the plan for with implementation of the business idea, by answering the following questions:

- Which development activities are planned for the product to be market-ready?
- Which marketing & sales activities are planned?
- How will you protect the product uniqueness?
- What will you do yourself, and what will you buy in? Are there involved external parties? How will you deal with related Intellectual Property Rights?
- What financial assumptions is your business plan based on?
- How large is the company's capital requirement until break-even? How much cash will be needed in the worst case?
- Where will that capital come from?
- What does the deal look like for potential investors? What return can investors expect? How will they realize their profits?

5.2 Implementation template

Table 5 Implementation phase template

Product Development plan
<p><u>Current stage of development:</u> Describe the current development stage of the project: prototyping, pilot studies, tests in simulated or operating environments, results obtained and conclusions. Add images of the product / service and results of significant tests.</p> <p><u>Next Development Steps to commercialize the product:</u> List the stages of product development foreseen up to commercialization, starting from the current stage, including all types of required activities (development, piloting, certification, integration, ..).</p>
Marketing and sales plan
<p><u>Target market size:</u> Estimate the available size of the market and the growth rate (specify if it is a mature or growing market), specify what the market trends are and what is your envisaged market share (specify the geographical focus)..</p> <p><u>Plan for commercialisation:</u></p>

Describe the initial plan that the company plans to follow for the commercialization of the product. Specify what the company can do internally and for which activities it requires support from third parties. Describe how the product / service addresses European and / or global markets, specify why your business model is scalable and what implementations should the company do to be able to scale the market.

Intellectual Property

IPR Items:

Describe the patent analysis performed by the company and the results of the analysis (for example: there are other patents on the same subject or no other patent has been filed). Specify whether the company already owns a patent or has submitted a patent application. In this case, specify who owns it, indicating the filing date and number. If not, please specify how you intend to protect your product and know-how. In case the idea can be patented but for strategic reasons the company decides not to do it, justify the reasons.

Knowledge management and protection:

What is your strategy for knowledge management and protection? If you have a patent, indicate the patented claims and where they apply.

Financials and investment plan

Financial plan:

Make an economic and financial plan to indicate the expected growth potential of the product / service in terms of turnover, jobs, market penetration, IP management, sales, return on investment and profits, etc.

Indicate fixed costs (personnel, infrastructure...), the variable cost of the product / service, the selling price of the product / service, the sales units, the expected market penetration.

Funding requirements:

Indicate the estimated funding requirements (and related timing) to reach the commercialization stage of your innovation. Indicate what are the plans to ensure the subsequent financing (e.g. bank, private investors, apply for EU Innovation funds, etc.).

5.3 Implementation methods and tools

Intellectual property protection

Although it is not always necessary or possible, it is important to protect innovative business ideas with Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). As mentioned in Section 3 of the Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement¹:

- Any result generated in the project are owned by the participant generating it, and if generated jointly it is also owned jointly.
- Jointly owned rights must be agreed on by the owners. Under some specific rules it is also possible to transfer rights to a third party.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=217

- The Commission may also protect results on behalf of the European Union if they are not protected other way.

The CLUSTERS 2.0 Consortium Agreement sets further rules in relation to:

- The IPR regarding any original contribution or background knowledge brought in by any member of the Consortium.
- The IPR regarding any new knowledge (forward knowledge) generated in the framework of CLUSTERS 2.0 as a result of any cooperative activity.

To be able to exploit new businesses based on CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions, the partners should first identify whether these are based on forward knowledge jointly developed with other partners. If this is the case, specific agreements should be established with the involved partners, setting the legal framework for:

- Joint exploitation of the results, based on common business and exploitation plans.
- Reciprocal acknowledgement of the involved partners' IPRs. This should translate into payment of royalties or license fees to those partners who have IPRs and do not take part in the commercial exploitation.

A further aspect to be considered in this phase is knowledge protection, i.e., how the partners' intellectual property generated in the project will be protected in its unique aspects. Possible protection methods include patents, trademarks, copyrights and utility models.

Patents are the most commonly used method to protect products. They are common for physical products but more to apply on software. *Trademark* is normally used to protect a name or a logo of a product but not the product itself. *Copyright* is typically used to protect knowledge (writings, artistic work) but in some cases it has been applied to source code of computer software. A *utility model* is similar to a patent, the main differences being the time of validity and the requirements for its granting.

Financial planning

Once the strategy, business model, market size and product development requirements are clear, the final step is to prepare a financial plan based on all these assumptions. The financial plan has the purpose of setting a realization schedule and providing a baseline for the financing, and assessing the related risks, of your business.

Realistic financial planning is important because:

- you can win credibility with investors and partners;
- you increase your enterprise's chances of success by thinking through the various activities and their interrelationships;
- you do not risk to endanger your company by investing on wrong- and in particular, too optimistic- targets.

The financial plan should contain information on the company's future financial development, backed up with a rough projection of the business economic performance. Detailed financial calculations are not necessary, as forecasts are by their nature approximate, and even more so for a new company.

The core of the financial plan is constituted by the assumptions made to plan for the business idea implementation, taking into account the available resources and organization and the expected market evolution. This allows setting a scenario for the implementation of the business idea, providing quantitative estimations for the main business variables over a sufficiently long time-horizon. The assumptions to be made cover three main areas:

Capital investments

The first set of assumptions concern the amount of money it will take to launch the business successfully. Based on the key resources identified in the business model, the following costs have to be estimated:

- Assets acquisition (e.g., hardware, software licences, patents, buildings, infrastructures, ..),
- Start-up costs and other one-time expenses.

Fixed expenses

The second set of assumptions is about fixed expenses, typically calculated on a monthly basis. This will allow estimating how much cash you need to have available at any given moment, for the business to be able to meet its current liabilities. Such expenses include:

- Personnel costs (both direct and indirect),
- Rental fees, services, insurances and other recurring expenses.

Sales forecast

Finally, the expected sales volumes have to be estimated, based on the identified customer segments and the potential market estimation carried out in the previous stages. Sales forecasts are among the most important assumptions to be included in a business plan, since they allow estimating:

- Revenues, calculated multiplying the unitary price by the monthly, quarterly or yearly sales forecasts.
- Cost of goods sold, calculated multiplying the unitary cost by the forecasted sales volumes.

The accuracy of such estimations is subject to large uncertainty, especially on the long-term and for an innovative business. Hence figures are not to be estimated at a very high level of detail, but should allow quantitative evaluation of the required investments, expected returns and related risks.

If the uncertainty is particularly high it might be useful to provide estimations for more alternative scenarios, e.g., a conservative “worst case” scenario and a “best case” scenario. To this purpose approaches and tools are available that support multi-criteria analysis of alternative scenarios, e.g., through simulation techniques.

These and other tools and approaches for business planning are available in literature. Financial planning is a widely studied subject with many consolidated approaches and standardized formats for, e.g., financial tables preparation. For the purposes of CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation planning a simple financial plan template, including indicators, has been prepared and attached to this guide as Annex 1.A.4, also including an application example.

Financial indicators

The financial plan data are also very useful as it allows to calculate indicators on the business financial performance. These indicators are very important as they allow business partners and potential investors to evaluate the business idea potential value and risks.

Professional investors normally require a small number of well thought out key figures. When presenting your business to executive-level managers and entrepreneurs you must be prepared to answer the following questions:

- How much money does the business need until it will be able to self-sustain its growth (time to break-even)?
- When break-even is reached, how much profit is the business likely to make?

- Which are the main assumptions that the forecasts are based on?

To this purpose, we propose the adoption of two main indicators that are commonly used for investments planning and evaluation:

Net Present Value (NPV)

The net present value is an estimation of an investment worth based on cash-flow estimations. Given the projected cash flow over a number of time periods, the NPV is the actualized net gain realized by the investment, taking into account the discount rate and the actual duration of the investment.

The formula for NPV calculation is:

$$NPV = \sum \frac{NV_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

where:

NV_t is the net cash flow at period t .

r is the discount rate applied for actualization of financial figures.

Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

The Internal Rate of the Return, also called Rate of Return (ROR) is a measure of an investment's profitability and is a common method to estimate the return on investment. It is calculated as the interest rate that, applied to a certain investment, makes the investment's Net Present Value (NPV) equal to zero. The higher the rate of return, the more profitable is to invest on a project or business idea.

The IRR can be calculated by solving the equation:

$$\sum \frac{NV_t}{(1+r)^t} = 0$$

where r is the IRR.

Computerized methods for calculating the IRR are widely available, including a pre-defined function available in Microsoft Excel.

The two indicators have the advantage of being directly calculable from common business planning assumptions and data. Also, these indicators can be applied indifferently to assess business plans for the launch of new products or companies, as well as to evaluate the returns of investment from a company's internal perspective, e.g., investments in CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions made by the partners after the project completion.

Conclusions

The exploitation process of CLUSTERS 2.0 consists of three main phases. It begins with product idea definition and it is followed by business strategy definition and business implementation planning. Each phase consists of several actions that should be carried out in order to proceed consistently to the next phase.

Most important is the identification of potential business ideas since the initial stages of the project, and of the relevant partners who will have to be involved in the exploitation of the idea. As each partner has different products, markets, visions, objectives, strategies and business plans, they will take an individual perspective on the exploitation. Nevertheless, for some business ideas to work on the market, different collaborating partners will be needed. In these cases it is highly recommended that joint exploitation plans are produced even, if necessary, involving external stakeholders if these are essential to the exploitation.

As pointed out in CLUSTERS 2.0 Deliverable D1.1, actors in the business ecosystem may need to change their business models to take advantage of the innovative solutions developed in the project. This should be taken into account by the partners when preparing their exploitation plans. They should first identify their role in the business ecosystem and then consider whether a change of business model is needed to achieve their ambitions. To this purpose the two Deliverables D1.1 and D1.2 are expected to be used for exploitation planning alongside this guide.

This document is meant to provide an overall frame for the exploitation process but ultimately each participant may and should apply tools, methods and metrics of their own preferences. Nevertheless it is important that the template format proposed in this document is used in all exploitation plans.

As next step of the CLUSTERS 2.0 exploitation process workshops will be organised for the partners to discuss their product ideas and plans. These workshop will start-up the actual process, leading to definition of exploitation plans in their draft and then final form that will be released as Deliverable D1.5.

References

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- [4] “The Innovator’s Solution: Creating and Sustaining Successful Growth”, Clayton M. Christensen and Michael E. Raynor, Harward Business School Press, 2003.
- [5] Nicholas G. Carr, “IT doesn’t matter”, Harward Business Review, May 2003 issue.
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A.1 Identifying needs with a “job tree”

A “job tree” is a tool introduced by Christensen and co-authors on Harvard Business Review in the scope of their “job to be done” theory of innovation.

The tree starts from a relevant but general need of the customer as root. The tree is then expanded adding as leafs more detailed “job”, i.e., better identified needs and circumstances originating from their parent leaves. The tree exploration stops when the leaves are sufficiently detailed, i.e., the needs and circumstances are defined with sufficient precision to be the start of our business ideas.

Example

The urban deliveries truck company might have a job tree as the one in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Job tree example

A.2 Blue Ocean Strategy approach for competitive positioning

The strategy canvas, as shown in Figure 2, allows assessing a new product competitiveness, capturing the current state of play in the market. This allows to pinpoint the features where the competition is currently investing, the factors the industry currently competes on in its products, services and how these are delivered to customers on the market.

Furthermore, it helps to assess whether our strategy is a good one, i.e., it has focus, diverges from competition, and can be easily transmitted into a compelling tagline or “elevator pitch”².

Our example in Figure 2 above looks as a case of “me too” strategy. We provide similar solutions as the marketplace providers, only focused on a specific geographic area and functionality.

This situation is quite well represented in the strategy canvas:

- Lack of focus (the curve is made of peaks and valleys), which indicates a possibly inconsistent strategy;
- The curve mirrors that of competitors (marketplaces), which indicates a “me too” strategy. We appear as just another marketplace offer;
- No compelling tagline: it is difficult to synthesise this configuration of performance attributes into a compelling message for the end customers;
- No differentiation:
 - o Small and medium freight carriers will continue preferring the traditional forwarders channel, which has no additional cost;
 - o We have no clear advantage over current marketplace solutions for large companies, to whom global reach is a major concern.

Five directions for revising your strategy

To improve your strategy, you should consider your solution current position on the market and try and find ways to break out of a not-too-comfortable position.

To this purpose, the Blue Ocean approach suggests to explore along six paths to differentiate from competition and thus expand your solution potential for success:

- Look across alternative industries
- Look across alternative segments
- Look across the value chain
- Look across complementary products/services
- Look at functional/emotional appeal
- Look across time.

1. Look across alternative industries

Seen from our company or product perspective, the market is formed by well delimited industries or sectors: e.g., software, hardware, system integration, logistics services.

² “An elevator pitch or elevator speech is an overview of a product, service, person, group or organization, or project and is often a part of a fundraising, marketing communications, brand, or public relations program.” (from Wikipedia.org)

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From the user's perspective, industry boundaries are much less evident. As a user looks for solutions to a "job to be done", he/she usually compares alternatives from different industries.

The first path to improve our strategy consists in looking across solutions from different industries, to find and combine winning elements from each of them.

Example

In Figure 2 strategy we appear as one more marketplace competing with other similar companies.

While the online marketplace offering may appeal to more sophisticated customers, many users, especially SMEs, find the offer from traditional physical intermediaries particularly attractive for the main reason that it has null set-up costs, as it is the usual way to do business in the sector.

As a first step to improve our strategy, we may think to change our positioning from "e-marketplace" to turnkey provider of logistic services involving for the carriers and shippers, eliminating the cost for them to adapt to the new system.

2. Look across market segments

A common tendency is that of splitting the target market into ever-smaller segments in an attempt to differentiate from competition. This creates specialized solutions dedicated to specific customer categories (e.g., based on investment capacity: small accounts, medium companies, large accounts).

As a second way to break out of constrained market space, you should consider to look across segments, e.g., to focus on performance attributes that are simultaneously attractive to different user categories in our target market.

Example

In our case we thought a good idea to start from the market of small carriers who offer city delivery services. As this market can be difficult to reach due to the above limitations, we might look to other customer segments. For example, large forwarders might be interested in using our platform to deal with city logistics, and could be able to involve the small carriers through their existing commercial networks.

3. Look across the value chain

A further option to increase the solution competitiveness is trying to go against the tendency to focus on a single role in the value chain. This is typical of established businesses that have pinpointed a category of users as the only buyers of their solution, and tend to focus all their efforts on finding the best way to appeal to these buyers.

In reality, buyer decisions are often affected by their position in a complex value chain, where the final product or service involves contributions from different companies and individuals.

To expand your solution potential market, you should consider to look across the value chain, e.g., to look for performance attributes that matter not just to your target customer, but to his partners upstream or downstream the value chain.

Example

In our case we have focused on carriers and shippers, but why not thinking about retail chains and shop owners who are the end users of the delivery business? They could be involved on the platform as well, going from a conventional 2-sides intermediation to a full 3-sides matching platform.

4. Look across complementary products and services

Products often are conceived as if they should be used in a vacuum. This is usually not true,

since users will have to complement our solution with other products or services to get the job done.

Hence, further ideas to improve our strategy may come from the analysis of complementary products and services that may have to be combined with our solution for it to work properly.

Example

To be done properly, cargo bundling in city deliveries would benefit of the use of Modular Load Units. These would increase bundling opportunities and facilitate handling operations. Why not thinking of a combined offer, including our platform and modular units rental?

5. Look across time

Global trends, either industry-, society- or technology-related are likely to affect our target market in time. This means not just to adapt to changes as they happen, e.g., release a new version of a product to include a new technology or standard.

We should look instead for trends that are likely to change the way users approach the problem we are trying to solve. When these trends will reach maturity they will have a disruptive impact on the market: companies whose solutions are incompatible with the new trend will be thrown out of business, while new companies will emerge through the ability to fit into the new scenario.

Example

City distribution can be affected by policy choices, e.g., creation of city hubs to decouple and re-organize cargo flows directed into the city. This will surely affect the delivery carriers business, and we should consider our platform role in facilitating the users in the transition when this will happen.

The Four Actions Framework

If we look at the process described above and at the changes applied to our strategy, we can see that these changes are meant to answer four basic questions:

- Which of the factors that the industry takes for granted should be eliminated?
- Which factors should be reduced, i.e., given less relevance than what they have in competing solutions?
- Which factors should be raised, i.e., given more relevance than what they have in competing solutions?
- Which factors should be created, i.e., new elements in our offer that are not available in competing solutions?

By listing the actions taken in each of the four categories we can easily verify and communicate the main innovative elements in our strategy, as shown in Figure 4.

In each step in our strategy definition process we take decisions about taking one or more of the above actions, at the end resulting in one focused, distinctive and clearly motivated strategy (Figure 5).

Figure 4 Example four actions framework

Figure 5 Revised competitive positioning

A.3 Osterwalder Business Model canvas

A.4 Financial Plan template and example

The following Figure 6 presents a simple five-years financial plan template. The template is available to CLUSTERS 2.0 partners in MS Excel format.

Financial Plan < Company name/ Product name/ Project name >					
Anno	1	2	3	4	5
Costs					
Capital investments	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Fixed expenses	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Cost of goods sold	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Revenues					
Sales volume (units)	0	0	0	0	0
Turnover	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
Cash flow					
Cash flow	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Cumulative Cash Flow	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Actualized cash flow					
Discounted Cash Flow (Present Value)	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Discounted Cumulative Cash Flow	€0	€0	€0	€0	€0
Net Present Value	€0				
Internal Return Rate (IRR)	#NUM!				

Assumptions made in this financial plan

Customer acquisition strategy	...
Cost per acquisition / 1 client	...
Marketing strategy	...
Revenue sources	...
Churn rate (& lost customers monthly)	...
Other	...

Investments planned

R&D Investments fir product development	...
Marketing investments	...

Figure 6 Financial plan template

Example

As an example application of the above indicators, we start from some hypothetical assumptions on a business plan based on the CluCS system, as one of the CLUSTERS 2.0 that will be subject to exploitation. All the assumptions and figures are just for the example sake and are in no way related to any real business that could be launched on the CluCS system.

Capital investments

The business requires a significant investment to extend, revise and integrate the research prototype out of the project, making it ready for actual use in the target industrial context. It is expected that this will require about 1 year and half, and 1.15 M€ investments in development and ICT infrastructure.

Fixed expenses

Fixed expenses per year are estimated as follows:

- 500 k€ for employees salaries;
- 15 k€ for building rental;
- 50 k€ for marketing expenses;

- 5 k€ for other expenses.

Sales forecast

Sales forecasts are based assuming a 20€ transaction fee, as average % on all transaction processed through CluCS. The number of transactions is estimated at 50.000 in the first year, growing by 10% on yearly basis.

Of these, the direct cost of goods is estimated at 10% for royalties paid on a transaction basis.

The following table shows the NPV and IRR calculation for our example, assuming an annual discount rate of 3,5%. As we can see, although the cash flow is negative for the first two years the investment looks quite attractive, with a Net Present Value of over 2.8 M€ and a return on investment (calculated as IRR) of 49%.

Of course these results are highly dependent on our assumptions, especially on sales forecasts that are the most subject to uncertainty. Therefore it is advisable to evaluate different scenarios corresponding, e.g., to different revenue estimations.

Financial Plan CluCS example					
Anno	1	2	3	4	5
Costs					
Capital investments	€750.000	€400.000	€0	€0	€0
Fixed expenses	€570.000	€570.000	€570.000	€570.000	€570.000
Cost of goods sold	€0	€100.000	€220.000	€242.000	€266.200
Revenues					
Sales volume (units)	0	50.000	110.000	121.000	133.100
Turnover	0 €	1.000.000 €	2.200.000 €	2.420.000 €	2.662.000 €
Cash flow					
Cash flow	-€1.320.000	-€70.000	€1.410.000	€1.608.000	€1.825.800
Cumulative Cash Flow	-€1.320.000	-€1.390.000	€20.000	€1.628.000	€3.453.800
Actualized cash flow					
Discounted Cash Flow (Present Value)	-€1.275.362	-€65.346	€1.271.739	€1.401.279	€1.537.275
Discounted Cumulative Cash Flow	-€1.275.362	-€1.297.580	€18.039	€1.418.708	€2.908.007
Net Present Value	€2.869.585				
Internal Return Rate (IRR)	49%				

Figure 7 Financial plan with indicators - example